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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL RESEARCH TO DETERMINE THE
INCIDENCE OF SMOKING AMONG WOMEN AND
THE HIGHLIGHT OF VARIOUS FACTORS ASSOCIATED
WITH IT****¹Dr. Hamda Bint e Shahzad, ²Dr. Abdul Ghafoor, ³Dr. Sara Iqbal**¹WMO, BHU Salar Bhattian Safdarabad Sheikhpura²Punjab Medical College Faisalabad³Sargodha Medical College.**Abstract**

Introduction: The habit of smoking in the community is a serious problem which is increasing day by day. Smoking is a term used to intake of the smoke of the burning tobacco. Tobacco may be in the form of cigarette, pipes and cigars. A person is called a smoker if he inhaled about 100 cigarettes. This habit is followed on daily basis are some day. Passive smoking is a mixture of mid-stream smoke and diluted mainstream smoke. Passive smoking is an automatic intake of smoke by a person who is not a smoker.

Objective: The objective of the study is to highlight the different factors connected with the habit of smoking in women.

Material and Methods: Our cross-sectional research was carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from April to October 2017. In this cross-sectional survey, 80 people were selected. After the written agreement, females were choosing on the basis of criteria. The selected was made from the local community. A questionnaire was arranged for taking interviews of females. By using SPSS, information was gathered, composed and assessed.

Results: Mostly young females were addicted to smoking. The result indicates the percentage of active smokers to be 17.5% and that of passive smokers to be 82.5%. The standard deviation calculated was 2.279 and mean age calculated was 21.91 years. The families of all the selected females (100%) were living together without any difference. The females with joint family were 17.5% and the females who are not living as a joint family were 82.5%. The participant who had affectionate parent was 11.3% while 88.8% participant was found with harsh parents. 6.3% of cases are found with narrowed eyes due to smoking. The parents of the participant who were addicted to smoking were 88.8%. however, the sibling of a participant who gets the habit of smoking was 27.5%. stress, depression and anxiety were present in 15%, 42.5% and 31.3% of cases respectively.

Conclusion: The study concludes that young age, inherent family system, smoking in parents and harshness of parents were the factors that lead to smoking habit in females.

Keywords: Determinants, females, smoking, psychosocial.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Hamda Bint e Shahzad,
WMO, BHU Salar Bhattian Safdarabad,
Sheikhpura.

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

The habit of smoke and it's widespread usually elevate in the age of below twenty. A person is called as a smoker if he or she is inhaling the smoke of cigarette at least 100 times in lifetimes. Either smoking is done on daily basis during the time of survey [1]. It is difficult to get rid of smoking in teenage and there is a possibility to becomes routine smokers [2]. Smoking in females is caused by a number of factors. These factors may include stress to control weight and announcement [3]. The families that are completely secured from the smoking are two percent [4]. The habit of smoking has often been observed in females with a high standard of living [5]. The females have enough amount of money to spend on cigarettes. Among other factors, the insufficient amount of money is the leading factor [6]. The environment of family matters a lot in catching habit of smoking. The family related factor responsible for addiction to smoking includes the style of parents, their assistance, closeness and their administration. The habit of smoking in females was increased because parents are unaware of friends of their child's and lack of time for their children [7] illegal smoking in females was concerned with the unrestricted diverted environment of the family [8]. Due to regular smoking and its management leads to squinting of eyes in females. To withstand inducement from peers to smoke is very hard [9]. The significant factors that lead to the habit of smoking are depression, anxiety and related factors [10]. Psychological depression is proceeded due to failure in adopting the change in life [11]. This stress and its related factors are mentioned several times that start and managed smoking [12, 13]. In some cases, stress is not a direct reason for smoking however, stress can be associated with some other factors [14, 15]. So, to organize this study for assessment and management of this severe issue that is increasing day by day is a need for the hour.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Our cross-sectional research was carried out at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad from April to October 2017. The aim of this cross-sectional study was to highlight different aspects that cause smoking in women. The females selected for this study, 80 females were selected. The social effect that one person exerts on the other is the Peer pressure. The family comprising a mother, father and their children is called as a nuclear family. The emotion performance thought and physical state of person altered by stress. In the state of stress, person feels lazy in doing work and is in the state of low mood. Anxiety is a psychological state. Simatic mental, physical and behavioural factor explained the state of anxiety. Passive smoking is a term used for the intake of smoke without smoking actually. This includes inhaling smoke from burning cigarette. To indicate stress, anxiety and depression, ICD 10 classification was used [16]. Using the pretested questionnaire, the interview was taken and information was assembled by considering all ethical and social status. All the participant in this study signed a written agreement. Mean and standard were estimated for age. For all the variables, frequency and percentage were estimated. By mean age calculated was 21.91. the facilities of all selected females (100%) were living together without any differences. The females with the joint family system was 17.5%and the females who are not living as a joint family were 82.5%. the participants who had affectionate parents were 11.3% while 88.8% of participants were found with harsh parents. 6.3% of cases are found with narrowed eyes due to t smoking. The parents of the participants who were addicted to smoking were 88.8%. however, the siblings of participants who got the habit of smoking were 27.5%. stress, depression and anxiety were present in 15%, 42.5% and 31.3% of in 15%, 45% and 31.3% of cases respectively. all the females choose for this study were Muslims, students and unmarried. The females with a high standard of living were 30% and the females with middle living standard were 70%.

Table: Various Psychosocial Determinants

Psychosocial Determinants	Number	Percentage
Nuclear Family Structure	66	82.50
Strict Attitude of Parents	71	88.80
Conflict among Parents	0	0.00
Smoking of Parents	71	88.80
Smoking of Siblings	22	27.50
Peer pressure	5	6.30
Stress	12	15.00
Anxiety	34	42.50
Depression	25	31.30

DISCUSSION:

This study indicates that the rate of passive smokers in our study is increasing day by day. The percentage of passive smokers in our study. However, 17.5% of females are an active smoker. Most of the population of females is passive smoker [17]. It is because of the tradition of tobacco smoking in men that leaves effects over females are mostly found addicted to smoking. The age of females was from 18 to 24years [18]. our study also includes mostly young females and the mean age recorded was 21.91. the study previously organized show similar outcomes as our

study that showed the females who had a nuclear family system was 82.5%. 88.8% of the participants are more addicted to smoking because of uncloseness their parents. On the other hand, females 11.3% with close parents are less addicted to smoking. by developing strong relationships with the children, setting clear rules and by strictly checking the children’s attitude and performance parents can retard the possibility of daily smoking (Robinson LA) [19]. This study indicates that children are affected by the behaviours of their parents. Those girls try to develop acute smoking who had parents accepted to

smoking as compared with the girls with parents who do not smoke [20]. A similar study was also conducted in Karachi. This study showed that smoking and spending directly associated with smoking habits in children [21]. Company of friends addicted to smoking also leads to a habit of smoking. A valuable connection between smoking and peer smoking is shown by the study organized in Karachi [21]. Social association also leads to a habit of smoking. Most of the people got the habit of smoking first from their friends. This is indicated in the study organized by Bricker and Colleagues [22]. In Brazil, another study was organized. This study is indicating that in order to get rid of stress, females are addicted to smoking [23]. Anxiety is a factor that cause smoking. Study organized in the past indicate that the smokers smoke to get rid of anxiety [23]. Depression is a factor that cause smoking habit in 31.1% of females according to the result of our study [24].

CONCLUSION:

The study concludes that young age, inherent family system, smoking in parents and harshness of parents were the factors that lead to smoking habit in females.

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